

NUMERICAL PIPELINE TO SIMULATE DRUG-COATED BALLOON TREATMENT IN ATHEROSCLEROTIC PERIPHERAL ARTERIES

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Introduction

Drug-coated balloon (DCB) therapy has recently emerged as an appealing non-stent-based strategy for the treatment of atherosclerotic arteries in peripheral artery disease (PAD), based on the “leave-nothing-behind” concept. Recent clinical evidence indicates that pre-treating the lesion with conventional balloons angioplasty plays a crucial role in adequately preparing the vessel footprint for subsequent drug-coating delivery to the target lesion. Both in lesion preparation and DCB treatment, the mechanical aspects underlying the balloon-vessel wall interaction could reveal the proper operating condition to enhance the DCB treatment efficacy. In this scenario, the present study aims to develop an accurate numerical pipeline to simulate lesion preparation in atherosclerotic peripheral arteries followed by DCB inflation in the pre-dilated vessels.

Materials and methods

A reliable Finite Element (FE) model of the lesion preparation treatment was developed according to the following steps.

i) A FE model of a balloon angioplasty commonly adopted for peripheral arteries was developed and the processes of folding and pleating were simulated. The 5-folded balloon configuration was validated by comparing the numerical result with the real balloon cross-section embedded in epoxy resin.

ii) Accurate FE models of peripheral stenotic arteries composed of 2 discrete layers (media and adventitia) with heterogeneous plaques and different geometrical features were developed. To obtain a reliable vessel footprint with whom the DCB will interact in the next step, a phenomenological constitutive model able to mechanically describe the vessel lumen gain and stiffness after the pre-dilation was introduced. The phenomenological damage model included plasticity and described the progressive degradation of the vessel wall stiffness due to tissue injury at the high strain levels induced by balloon angioplasty. Moreover, a cohesive zone model approach able to describe arterial dissections and plaque delamination at the interfaces observed in clinical practice was introduced.

iii) The balloon angioplasty treatment has been simulated by inflating the 5-folded balloon model in the described stenotic arteries models. Calibration of the damage model parameters and evaluation of the balloon-vessel wall interaction were performed by

adopting 2D stenotic artery models with degrees of stenosis, plaque compositions and geometries consistent with peripheral arteries features.

Results

The analyses performed demonstrated that an accurate FE model of the folded balloon is essential to properly describe the balloon-vessel interaction [1]. In the case of high degrees of stenosis typical of peripheral arteries, indeed, the balloon started interacting with the lesion when it was still folded, leading to localized contact pressures and overstretching of the artery walls. Moreover, this effect propagated in the internal artery layers, resulting in high levels of tissue injury and dissections at the interfaces especially in the case of heterogeneous plaques (calcified and generic, as represented in Fig.1)

Discussion and conclusions

This work presents a novel numerical workflow to simulate lesion preparation in stenotic peripheral arteries followed by DCB inflation. The inclusion of a phenomenological constitutive model able to describe vessel injury proved to be essential for obtaining reliable pre-dilated artery models to be used for simulating the subsequent DCB treatment.

Figure 1: a) In-vitro and in-silico folded balloon cross-sections. State of damage at the interfaces at 30% of balloon inflation (b) and in the artery walls at 100% of balloon inflation (c)

References

1. Stratakos et al, Annals of Biomedical Engineering, 2023

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